

ELECTRODEPOSITION OF BRONZE FROM A CYANIDE BATH

By D. SINGH AND N. N. S. SIDDHANTA

Electrodeposition of bronze from a bath containing copper cyanide, sodium stannate, cyanide and hydroxide of sodium was studied with respect to electrolyte concentration, current density, duration of electrolysis, temperature and addition agents. The optimum conditions for a satisfactory deposit on copper with respect to these factors are as follows :

The electrolyte concentration is such that the ratio of copper to tin is 1:3. The optimum C. D. is 0.76 amp/dm². Cathode efficiency at the optimum C. D. is 62.5 %. Optimum duration of electrolysis is 20 minutes. Temperature of 60° is found to be the most suitable. Influence of addition agents like glycerol and sodium chloride is not well marked, though use of H₂O₂ improves the deposit.

The bright silvery coating of bronze is superior to that of nickel or tin for protecting iron, steel and other metals, as it is less susceptible to atmospheric corrosion. The electroplated alloy is surpassed only by freshly plated silver in reflectivity and it is highly resistant to abrasion. The alloy can be soldered as easily as tin. These and the like are some of the remarkable properties of the alloy which attracted the attention of the electroplater. The work of Baier and Macnaughtan (*J. Electrodep. Tech. Soc.*, 1936, 11, 14) and of Bechard (*Metal Progr.*, 1936, 29, No. 3, 43, 94 ; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1936, II, 2217) has shown that Cu-Sn alloy of different compositions can be deposited in a satisfactory and adhesive form from an alkaline solution of Na₂Cu(CN)₂ and Na₂SnO₃ at 65°, using either carbon or bronze anode. Bechard (*Compt. rend.*, 1935, 200, 1737) has also studied the electrodeposition of the alloy from solutions of stannic-ammonium and copper-ammonium oxalates. The information available in the literature on the quantitative data for bronze deposition is very meagre. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to study the deposition of the alloy quantitatively in regard to the influence of a number of factors.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electrolysis was carried out in a round glass trough, about 3" deep, and having a capacity of about 250 c.c. It was kept immersed in a thermostat and maintained at the desired temperature. The temperature of the bath solution was controlled within ±2°. The anode used was a well-cleaned thin plate of Cu-Sn alloy (80% Cu and 20% Sn) of size 3 × 2.5 sq. cm. A thin plate (5 × 2.5 cm. approx.) of Cu (99.5%) serving as the cathode was first rendered free from grease by dipping it in a hot 10% caustic soda solution for a few minutes and then washing it with water ; it was next immersed in moderately strong nitric acid to remove the surface scale. The plate was then washed with distilled water and finally with alcohol, dried and weighed accurately when necessary. A copper coulometer was used to give the measure of the quantity of electricity passed through the electrolyte. The coulometer solution was prepared according to Oettel's recommendations (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 543). The current was obtained from 220 volts D. C. mains ; the circuit consisted of an electrolyte bath, copper coulometer, a precision type milliammeter

and an adjustable resistance in series, and a voltmeter connected across the electrodes in the bath.

Two stock solutions were prepared : (A) by dissolving Merck's pure sample of $\text{Cu}(\text{CN})_2$ (62.8g.) and NaCN (137.2 g.) in 1000 c. c. of distilled water ; (B) by dissolving $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (168.25 g.) and NaOH (200 g.) in 1000 c.c. of water. In all the following experiments these stock solutions were used after mixing the requisite quantities of (A) and (B), and with the appropriate additions of the other materials used in this work. To investigate the optimum conditions for a smooth, bright and adherent deposit of bronze the influence of the following factors has been studied over a wide range :

1. Electrolytic concentration in terms of metal ion content (Table IA). 2. Time (Table IB). 3. Current density (Table II). 4. Temperature (Table III). 5. Addition agents (Table IV).

The nature of the alloy deposit obtained in each of these experiments is also recorded as examined with a microscope. The cathode efficiency was calculated by the relation,

$$\% \text{Cathode efficiency} = \frac{100 \times \text{actual amount of the alloy deposited}}{\text{theoretical amount of the deposit}}$$

TABLE IA

Variation of the concentration of the electrolyte.

C. D. = 0.76 amp./dm². Time = 20 minutes. Temp. of the bath = 60° ± 2°. Interelectrode distance = 1 cm. $p_H = 12.5$ approx. Vol. of electrolyte = 200 c.c.

Metal ion conc.		Nature of deposit.
Copper.	Tin	
0.89001 g.	1.1388 g	Uniform, adherent and red coloured deposit with coarse grain structure
0.89001	1.7082	Good, bright and improved deposit with fine grain structure
0.89001	2.2777	Very good, bright, silvery, smooth, adherent and uniform deposit with fine grain structure.
0.89001	2.8471	Deposit becomes dull white, probably due to more of Sn being deposited.

TABLE IB

Variation of time.

Metal ion conc : Cu = 0.89001 g. Sn = 2.2777. C D. = 0.76 amp./dm². Temp. = 60° ± 2°. Interelectrode distance = 1 cm. $p_H = 12.5$ approx. Vol. of electrolyte = 200 c.c.

Time.	Nature of deposit.
5 min	Irregular crystals, red and shining deposit
10	Deposit shining and lustrous, fine grained and of uniform structure
15	Deposit bright, silvery, smooth, adherent and uniform
20	Still improved and highly satisfactory deposit
25	Deposit shows tendency to peel off and to become spongy and powdery
30	Deposit becomes black and being non-adherent, falls to powder on mere tapping the plate.

TABLE II

Effect of current density

Metal ion conc: Cu=0.89001 g. Sn=2.2777 g. Interelectrode distance=1 cm
 Temp. of the bath= $60^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. Time=20 mins $p_H=12.5$ approx. Vol of electrolyte
 =200 c.c.

C. D. (amp./dm ²)	Wt of alloy deposit.		Cathode efficiency.	Nature of deposit
	Obs.	Calc.		
0.64	0.0236g.	0.0614g.	38.4%	Reddish deposit, more of copper
0.68	0.0339	0.0653	52.0	Deposit becomes reddish white
0.72	0.0420	0.0691	60.8	Smooth, adherent, dull white deposit.
0.76	0.0467	0.0730	62.5	Good, bright, silvery, smooth, adherent deposit with fine grained structure
0.80	0.0470	0.0768	61.2	Deposit blackens in colour, less adherent with crevices.
0.84	0.0477	0.0806	59.2	Non-uniform deposit, has tendency to peel off, deep crevices.

TABLE III

Effect of temperature.

Metal ion conc: Cu=0.89001 g. Sn=2.2777 g. Interelectrode distance=1 cm:
 Temp. of the bath= $60^{\circ} \pm 2^{\circ}$. Time=20 mins. $p_H=12.5$ approx. Vol. of electrolyte
 =200 c.c.

Temp.	Wt. of alloy deposit		Cathode efficiency.	Nature of deposit.
	Obs.	Calc.		
20°	0.0234 g.	0.0730 g.	32.1%	Smooth, bright, dull yellow deposit.
30°	0.0322	0.0730	44.1	Deposit of the same nature, but of golden yellow colour like brass.
40°	0.0367	0.0730	50.7	Do
50°	0.0418	0.0730	57.3	Deposit becomes reddish yellow in colour.
60°	0.0456	0.0730	62.49	Smooth, bright, silvery, adherent and uniform deposit with fine structure.
70°	0.0449	0.0730	61.6	Slightly burnt deposit.
80°	0.0443	0.0730	60.7	Burnt deposit.

TABLE IV

Effect of addition agent.

Metal ion conc: Cu=0.89001 g. Sn=2.2777 g. Interelectrode distance=1 cm.
Temp. of the bath=60°±2°. Time=20 min. p_H =12.5 approx. Vol. of electrolyte
=200 c.c.

Addition agent (A).	Amount of (A) in 1000 c.c. of soln.	Wt. of alloy deposit		Cathode efficiency	Nature of deposit.
		Obs.	Calc.		
Glycerol	5 c.c.	0.0456 g.		62.5%	Satisfactory deposit of bronze.
	10	0.0454		62.2	Deposit slightly turns yellow.
	20	0.0454	0.0730 g.	62.2	Yellow colour increases.
	30	0.0450		61.7	Yellow, brass coloured deposit.
NaCl	5 g.	0.0456		62.5	Bright, silvery, adherent and uniform deposit.
	10	0.0458		62.7	Improved deposit.
	20	0.0464		63.4	" "
	30	0.0478	0.0730 g.	65.6	" "
	40	0.0474		64.9	Deposit becomes dull and dark.
	50	0.0466		63.7	Increasingly dark deposit.
H ₂ O ₂	5 c.c.	0.0456		62.5	Good deposit.
	10	0.0462		63.3	Deposit improves in brightness and uniformity.
	20	0.0480	0.0730 g.	65.8	Still further improvement in the deposit.
	30	0.0486		66.5	Do
	40	0.0484		66.48	Do
	50	0.0480		65.9	Deposit shining and uniform, but slightly blackening effect.

DISCUSSION

The results in Table I A show that silvery, bright, lustrous and adherent deposit with fine grained structure is obtained from the bath solution containing the metal ion concentration: Cu, 0.89001 g., Sn, 2.2777 g. at the C.D. employed; stronger and dilute solutions are found to yield less satisfactory results. The copper and tin ions of the plating solution are furnished by the double copper cyanide and sodium stannate; the salts dissociate as:

This ionisation produces no copper or tin ions, but the complexes further ionise to a very small extent,

There is thus produced a favourable condition for electrodeposition; the metal ion concentration is low, but there is an inexhaustible reserve supply to replace the few metallic ions as fast as they are removed.

Our results in Table I B show that with the increase of time (up to 20 mins.) the deposit becomes finer. Adhesivity is also improved. It is interesting to note that at constant C.D., concentration, temperature etc., the deposit, which is initially bright and adherent, tends to become, as the time elapses, loose, powdery, non-adhesive and black (cf. Table I B). This can be attributed to the increased alkalinity of the bath due to high anodic efficiency with the progress of electrolysis and subsequent inclusion of the basic hydroxide in the cathode deposit. Kurda's findings (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, 178, 377) lead to similar conclusions.

The data recorded in Tables II, III and IV show that the nature and magnitude of an electrodeposit is influenced by a number of physicochemical factors. These are discussed conveniently in respect of cathode efficiency which is 100% under ideal

FIG. 1

conditions. Its diminution is chiefly due to the occurrence of side reactions, e.g., evolution of hydrogen at the cathode, or the formation of molecular or ionic complexes in the conducting system. The results in Table II (cf. curve I in Fig. 1) show that at constant values for concentration and temperature the current density exerts a pronouncedly marked influence on cathode efficiency of the bronze deposition which varies within wide limits from 38.4% at C.D. 0.64 amp./dm² to 62.5% at C.D. 0.76 amp./dm². Very low efficiency at low C.D. is ascribable to the appreciable part of the current being utilised in discharging hydrogen at the cathode. With increase in C.D. up to 0.76 amp./dm² this evolution is appreciably inhibited due to the corresponding increase in the hydrogen overvoltage; with further increase in C.D. (0.76 amp./dm² to 0.84 amp./dm²) the efficiency diminishes obviously due to hydrogen evolution, caused by a rapid depletion of the metal in the cathode film during electrolysis. At low C.D. only copper is deposited at the cathode since the normal electrode potential of copper Π_{Cu} is considerably greater than Π_{Sn} in these solutions. With the increase in C.D. and temperature the deposition potentials of copper and tin from cyanide and alkaline stannate solution approach one another very closely. At C.D. 0.76 amp./dm² and 60°, the simultaneous deposition of the two metals is possible. Hence in order to obtain the alloy deposit, the C.D. over the whole cathode must not be less than 0.76 amp./dm² and the temperature of the bath must be more than 60° (Table III).

From a study of the data shown in Table III (cf. curve II, Fig. 1) at constant C.D. the quality of the deposit is seen to improve by increasing the temperature up to a certain extent (about 60°) and to deteriorate at higher temperature (80°). The cathodic efficiency also increases with rise in temperature steadily up to 60° and then slows down and remains almost constant at higher temperatures. Increase of temperature has two opposing effects: in the first place it favours the diffusion and tends to produce a uniform and fine grained deposit, but, on the other hand, it decreases the velocity of the crystal growth and thus fosters the formation of coarse deposits. At moderate temperature the influence of the first factor is generally predominating, but at higher temperatures the second is increasingly operative

The data recorded in Table IV show that there is no precise relation of the cathode efficiency with the proportions of an addition agent in the electrolytic bath. In presence of NaCl and H₂O₂, bright, lustrous deposits are obtained with increased efficiency (curves IV and V respectively, Fig. 1), possibly due to hydrogen evolution at the cathode being considerably arrested; their increased concentration, however, produces dark deposits. The addition in traces of glycerol (0.5%) gives satisfactory deposits but with the further addition the deposit becomes spoiled and the cathodic efficiency decreases slightly (curve III, Fig. 1).

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